

INFLUENCE OF HEAT TREATMENT ON PROPERTIES OF CdS–PbS THIN-FILM COMPOSITIONS OBTAINED ON CdS_(SOLID)/Pb²⁺_(AQUA) INTERPHASE

N. Forostyanaya¹, L. Maskaeva^{1,2}, Z. Smirnova¹, V. Markov^{1,2}

¹ Department of Physical and Colloid Chemistry, Ural Federal University named after the First President of Russia B.N. Yeltsin, Ekaterinburg, Russia

² Department of Chemistry and Combustion Processes, Ural Institute of State Fire Service of EMERCOM of Russia, Ekaterinburg, Russia

* Corresponding author (mln@ural.ru)

Keywords: *thin films, cadmium sulfide, solid solution, ionic exchange, heat treatment, hydrochemical deposition*

The composition, structure and morphology of multiphase semiconductor films of as-deposited cadmium sulfide and CdS films, incubated in the solution of lead acetate PbAc₂ have been investigated. The compositions based on cadmium sulfide, formed on CdS_(SOLID)/Pb²⁺_(AQUA) interphase, have been investigated by the methods of X-ray diffraction, electronic and atomic-powered microscopy. Changes of the structure and morphology of thin-film compositions after heat treatment at 423 K have been examined.

1 Introduction

One of the topical problems of materials science is modification of conventional materials for enhancement of their functional properties and performance. At present, cadmium sulfide, which evokes considerable interest, is among the most called-for materials. Thin films of wide-band-gap semiconductors such as CdS have low degradation stability. This lack essentially limiting areas of CdS applications can be eliminated by introduction of some of lead sulfide into a structure of polycrystalline CdS film [1].

Interest to research of a surface and interphases of threefold systems also is caused by an opportunity of occurrence of new properties, allowing to produce electronic instruments and devices with unique properties.

Cadmium sulfide is wide-band-gap semiconductor material (2.43 eV). It is widely used in diodes, lasers of a visible band and in photo-electric devices. Lead sulfide is relatively narrow-band-gap semiconductor (0.41 eV), and is used in infrared (IR) devices. The advantage of solid solutions in PbS-CdS system is the opportunity of smooth regulation of a band-gap by change of a structure, and, hence, regulation of optical and electro-physical properties. Threefold compounds, based on lead and cadmium sulfides in the forms of thin films draw special attention owing to an opportunity of their practical application in

optoelectronics, sun-protection coverings, gas and liquid sensor controls, photo-electric solar elements [2].

CdS-PbS film samples obtained by thermal evaporation of the working mixture, containing 90 mass % of CdS and 10 mass % of PbS, have high irradiation stability of photo-electric and electro-physical characteristics [3]. And it is marked [3–5] that heat treatment carried out after synthesis, changes structure and morphology of a surface of thin films. In a volume and on a surface of CdS-PbS hetero-phase material a number of processes connected to redistribution of lead sulfide and self-organizing of formation of solid solutions both from side of PbS, and from side of CdS occurs.

At consideration of a potential opportunity of formation of solid solutions in CdS-PbS system it was noticed, that it is impossible to recognize lead and cadmium as elements with favorable opportunities of isomorphic miscibility. Distinction of ionic radiuses makes about 24 %. Besides, individual sulfides of these elements crystallize in structures of various types: CdS forms cubic lattice of sphalerite *B3* (spatial group *F43m*), its high-temperature modification - wurtzite *B4* (spatial group *P63mc*); PbS has cubic lattice such as NaCl *B1* (spatial group *Fm3m*). Therefore lead and cadmium sulfides have the limited area of mutual solubility and form Pb_xCd_{1-x}S solid solutions only at small quantities of substitut-

ing component. According to the phase diagram the solubility of PbS in cadmium sulfide makes less than 0.1 mol % at 1203 K [6].

Polycrystalline photosensitive CdS-PbS films are obtained in vacuum by thermal evaporation of the working mixture, containing 90 mass % of CdS, 10 mass % of PbS and additive of CuCl₂ as the activator [3]. For production of substitutional solid solutions in this system the simple thrifty "soft-chemical" technological method such as chemical deposition from aqueous solutions can be used. By hydrochemical co-deposition of individual lead and cadmium sulfides at 353-363 K supersaturated Cd_xPb_{1-x}S solid solutions from the side of PbS (0.0 ≤ x ≤ 0.21) were obtained [7], while equilibrium solubility of CdS in PbS even at 523 K makes only 0.009 atomic %. Pb_xCd_{1-x}S (0.05 ≤ x ≤ 0.25) solid solutions from the side of cadmium sulfide were obtained by hydrochemical deposition [8]. One of the ways of changing of composition, structure and properties of films of metal sulfides and metal selenides is the modification of a surface of a thin film of a metal chalcogenide by its incubation in a salt solution of other metal. In particular, thin-film layer PbSe was modified by processing in tin chloride solution SnCl₂, containing additives of sodium citrate Na₃C₆H₅O₇ and sodium hydroxide NaOH (PbSe_(solid)/Sn²⁺_(aqua)) [9], in mercury salt water solution Hg(NO₃)₂ (PbSe_(solid)/Hg²⁺_(aqua)) [10], and semi-conductor layer PbS contacted to the silver salt solution AgNO₃ with additive of thiocarbamide N₂H₄CS (PbS_(solid)/Ag⁺_(aqua)) [11], with cadmium salt solution CdCl₂, ammonia NH₄OH and sodium citrate Na₃C₆H₅O₇ (PbS_(solid)/Cd²⁺_(aqua)) [12]. Thus the authors established the formation of substitutional solid solutions of metal chalcogenides.

For formation of *p-n* junctions in film solar elements CdS/Cu₂S it is offered to use ionic-exchange reactions of transformation of CdS into Cu₂S by immersing in CuCl solution [13], and in [14] the substitution of Cd²⁺ ions in CdS films is carried out not only by immersing in acid CuCl aqueous solution, but also by "dry" exchange process (solid CuCl was placed on CdS surface with the subsequent sticking). In [15] after exposition of hydrochemically deposited CdS layers in CuCl solution at 333 K during 10 seconds the ionic-exchange reaction has proved to be true by occurrence on roentgenograms of films besides the reflexes from CdS also the reflections from Cu₂S phase. For regulation of photosensitivity CdS films were immersed on 2 minutes in CuCl₂ and CdCl₂ water solutions with the subsequent annealing on air at 823 K during 1-7 minutes [16]. Though

about the course of ionic-exchange reactions nothing it is told, the exposition in CuCl₂ solution resulted in re-crystallization of the films. Experimental results [17] where it is informed about the carried out at 523 K annealing on air of modified in CuCl aqueous solution CdS films also testify about the same process. The method of X-ray diffraction shows amplification of intensity of reflexes of Cu₂S phase in the films.

With the purpose of modification of physical properties of CdS films they were immersed for some seconds in AgNO₃ aqueous solution, containing thio-sulfate complexes of metal, at neutral pH value of the medium [18]. Thus color of the films changed from orange-yellow up to gray-green. However, the results of X-ray diffraction analysis have shown, that in all samples there was only CdS phases of two modifications, and with increasing of exposition time in silver (I) solution the share of hexagonal phase increased.

Thus, the results of publications on processes of ionic-exchange substitution of lead in PbSe and PbS films, cadmium in CdS films on Sn²⁺, Hg²⁺, Ag⁺ Cd²⁺ and Cu²⁺ ions accordingly allow to conclude, that the researched method has wide prospects for change of composition, structure and electro-physical properties of thin films.

In connection with, the purpose of the present work was studying of physical and chemical laws of production of thin-film compositions based on cadmium and lead sulfides by the method of ionic-exchange substitution at "CdS film - lead salt aqueous solution" interphase and investigation of interrelations between the conditions of their production, composition, structure and morphology.

2 Experiment

2.1 Materials and methods

Thin films of cadmium sulfide of 250-300 nanometers thickness, obtained by hydrochemical deposition were used as initial material.

CdS films were deposited on preliminary degreased glass-ceramic substrates from the aqueous reactionary mixes containing cadmium chloride CdCl₂, complexing agents (sodium citrate Na₃C₆H₅O₇, ammonium hydroxide NH₄OH) and thiocarbamide CH₄N₂S. The reaction of formation of cadmium sulfide at deposition by thiocarbamide is:

The duration of CdS hydrochemical deposition at 333-353 K has made 90-120 minutes.

Synthesized CdS layers were incubated at temperatures from 293 up to 353 K in aqueous solutions of lead acetate PbAc₂, containing various complexing additives (sodium citrate Na₃C₆H₅O₇, ethylenediamine H₂NCH₂CH₂NH₂), by varying concentrations of reagents and duration of incubation in the reactionary bath from 1 till 9 hours.

It was supposed, that on “thin film - cadmium (II) salt aqueous solution” interphase will proceed heterogeneous topochemical ionic-exchange reaction described by the equation:

The thermodynamic criterion of an opportunity of reaction (2) is the difference of solubility products of cadmium (II) and lead (II) sulfides: $1.6 \cdot 10^{-28}$ and $2.5 \cdot 10^{-27}$ [19] accordingly. Thus the standard change of a free enthalpy, characterizing thermodynamic probability of ionic-exchange process in this system, makes

$$\Delta G_T^0 = -RT \ln K_d = -RT \ln \frac{\text{SP}_{\text{CdS}}}{\text{SP}_{\text{PbS}}} = -6.70 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}} \quad (3)$$

The obtained value of change of a free enthalpy does not allow judge the direction of the process unequivocally. Therefore with a view of definition of optimum conditions of ionic-exchange reaction (2) the way of aprioristic estimation of concentrations of reagents in the reactionary mix at which reaction (2) is optimum was offered. For this purpose the equation of isotherm of chemical reaction known from thermodynamics [20] was used.

In view of the transition of cadmium ions into the aqueous medium due to dissolution of initial CdS film owing to its interaction with strong complexing agent sodium citrate and in the assumption of absence of strong electrostatic interactions of ions in solution (factors of activity are close to one) the equation (3) may be written as:

$$\Delta G_T^0 = -RT \ln \left(\frac{[\text{Cd}^{2+}] \cdot \text{SP}_{\text{PbS}}^0}{[\text{Pb}^{2+}] \text{SP}_{\text{CdS}}^0} \right), \quad (4)$$

where [Pb²⁺], [Cd²⁺] - equilibrium concentrations of lead (II) and cadmium (II) ions in aqueous medium. Calculations according to the equation (4) have shown, that at increase of Na₃C₆H₅O₇ concentration up to 1.0 mol/L at room temperature the probability of ionic-exchange reaction grows with increase of pH from 0 up to 14 (fig. 1). By the results of the analysis of ionic equilibria, cadmium and lead near to minimum of ΔG_T exist mainly as complexes

with hydroxide- and citrate-ions. Formation of Pb_xCd_{1-x}S solid solution in these conditions is, on the one hand, the result of co-deposition of lead and cadmium sulfides at presence of thiocarbamide due to entering of cadmium ions into a liquid phase at ionic exchange and undercutting etching of initial CdS film. On the other hand, it is possible to assume a presence of a stage of solid-state diffusion of lead (II) ions from aqueous solution deep into the film on vacancies of CdS cation sublattice.

Heat treatment of the films was carried out in electric furnace "PM-1.0-7" with use of the following mode: samples placed in a furnace and slowly heated up from room temperature up to 423 K, exposed at this temperature within 120 minutes and then power switched out.

Fig.1. Dependence of ΔG_T of heterogeneous ionic-exchange substitution reaction in “CdS_{solid}/Pb²⁺_{aquea}” system from pH and [C₆H₅O₇³⁻]. Calculation was carried out for 298 K.

The phase composition and the structure of the films were examined using X-ray diffraction with CuK_α radiation on a DRON-UM1 (Russia) diffractometer. Data were collected for 2θ from 5° to 70° with a scan step of Δ(2θ) = 0.03° and a 5 seconds accumulation time for the signal at each point.

The morphology of the films was examined using scanning electron microscopy on a Scanning Electron Microscope JEOL JSM-6390 LV (Japan). The topography of samples was examined by the method

of atomic-powered microscopy (APM) on the part of the surface of the film with 40×40 microns size, at scanning in semi-contact mode on air at room temperature on probing microscope Ntegra Terma (Russia, NT-MDT).

Optical properties of the films were examined on IR-Fourier spectrometer Nicolet 6700 according to the method of the broken full internal reflection.

3 Results and discussion

According to analysis done above the optimum conditions for ionic-exchange process in $\text{CdS}_{\text{solid}}/\text{Pb}^{2+}_{\text{aqua}}$ system were determined. On SEM images of CdS films, exposed in lead salt solution (fig. 2) it is visible, that as a result of a chemical and ionic-exchange processes the formation of globules and aggregates which diameter reaches 1 micron, from 20-50 nanometers in size nanocrystallites occurs on their surface.

Fig.2. SEM-images of the initial CdS (a) and CdS incubated in the lead salt solution (b)

(a)

(b)

The X-ray diffraction patterns have revealed that all CdS films, incubated in the lead salt solution, contained phases, one of which was $\text{Pb}_x\text{Cd}_{1-x}\text{S}$ solid solution based on CdS with a B3 structure (fig. 3). The increase of duration of a contact of CdS film with lead (II) salt solution was accompanied by increase of CdS lattice spacing up to 0.5807 nanometers (parameters of primitive unit cells for individual cadmium and lead sulfides have made 0.5761 and 0.5929 nanometers, accordingly). The obtained data were interpreted as the result of substitution of Cd^{2+} -ions with 0.097 nanometers radius on Pb^{2+} -ions of greater radius (0.120 nanometers).

Heat treatment renders appreciable influence on phase structure of obtained $\text{Pb}_x\text{Cd}_{1-x}\text{S}$ solid solutions based on cadmium sulfide. After the heat treatment of $\text{Pb}_x\text{Cd}_{1-x}\text{S}$ films the reflections displaced to smaller angles, that, probably, specifies the increase of a share of lead sulfide in the structure of the substitutional $\text{Pb}_x\text{Cd}_{1-x}\text{S}$ solid solution. Reflections from (220) and (311) planes for as-deposited and heat-treated films of the cadmium sulfide, preliminary incubated in the lead salt solution, and the X-ray patterns of individual cadmium and lead sulfides are shown on fig. 3. It is visible, that intensity of inclusion of lead ions into the lattice of cadmium sulfide considerably grows at heat treatment of formed as a result of ionic-exchange multiphase CdS-PbS compositions.

Fig. 3. X-ray patterns of CdS, PbS, and CdS-PbS solid solution films before and after the heat treatment

The comparative analysis of X-ray diffraction patterns have revealed, that reflection peaks of cadmium sulfide films, and also of solid solutions on its basis were appreciably widened. Heat treatment promoted the narrowing of reflection peaks for CdS from 1.73 till 1.63 nanometers, and for $Pb_xCd_{1-x}S$ from 1.49 till 1.27 nanometers (fig. 4).

The widening of reflection peaks can be caused by three various reasons: by small sizes of areas of coherent scattering (or, as a first approximation by small sizes of crystallites), by strains and micro-deformations, and by heterogeneity of a structure.

Fig.4. Dependence of enumerated widening from the length of scattering vector for as-deposited (a) and heat-treated (b) films of $Pb_xCd_{1-x}S$ solid solution

Several methods of allocation of contributions into widening are offered in the literature. The method of Williamson-Hall allowing divide contributions in widening depending on a reason is described in [21]. For allocation of the dimensional and deformation

contributions in widening of a physical profile of diffraction reflections, the dependence of enumerated widening $\beta^*(2\theta)$ from the length of scattering vector $s = [2\sin\theta]/\lambda$ as linear function for as-deposited film (fig.4) was constructed.

The inclination of dependence $\beta^*(2\theta)$ characterizes the amount of micro-deformations in a sample, and sizes of grains results from extrapolating $\beta^*(2\theta)$ dependence on the value $s = 0$. The average size of the area of coherent scattering was determined according to Debye-Scherrer equation:

$$\langle D \rangle = \frac{K_{hkl}\lambda}{[\beta(2\theta)\cos\theta]} \cong \frac{\lambda}{[\beta(2\theta)\cos\theta]} \equiv \frac{1}{\beta^*(2\theta)}, \quad (5)$$

where K_{hkl} is the Scherrer constant, which depends on the form of a crystallite (particle, domain) and from indexes (hkl) of diffraction reflections; λ is the length of radiation wave. For cubic crystals $K_{hkl} \approx 1$ in first approximation.

Widening does not depend on the size of particles as extrapolation of the found $\beta^*(s)$ dependence on $\theta = 0^\circ$ gives equal to zero enumerated widening for as-deposited and heat-treated samples, hence, the particles in the structure of these compounds have big enough sizes which cannot be determined with the help of the X-ray analysis. As confirmation to this serve SEM-images (fig. 2) on which it is visible, that particles in the film of cadmium sulfide having sizes of about 0.25 microns at increase of incubation time in the lead salt solution forms agglomerates with the sizes up to 1.5 microns.

It is visible, that at increase of θ widening also increases. It means that there are micro-deformations in the films which are the reasons for widening. The amount of micro-deformations in samples can be estimated, analyzing the angle of straight line inclination at shown dependences. It is visible, that the angle of straight line inclination for heat-treated sample (Fig.4. b) is a little bit less than that for as-deposited sample (Fig.4. a), that testifies that at heat treatment the amount of micro-deformations decreases and ordering of the structure occur.

For research of the topography of the surface of obtained films, the method of atomic-powered microscopy (APM) was applied. Images of the most typical fragments of the surfaces of as-deposited and heat-treated samples, and also their three-dimensional views for CdS-PbS films are shown on fig.5 and fig.6.

Fig.5. APM-image in topography mode (a), and three-dimensional image of the surface of as-deposited CdS-PbS film (b).

It is visible, that all films have polycrystalline structure.

It was revealed, that the morphology of the layers essentially changed after heat treatment. It is possible to note, that the surface of as-deposited CdS-PbS films consisted of densely located aggregates with rounded forms with the sizes from 0.5 up to 1.5 microns, and also from the extended agglomerates reaching 3.0 microns in length which in turn are set of smaller particles. After heat treatment the surface of the film becomes more homogeneous, consisting of larger particles with rounded forms with the sizes about 2.7 microns. Integration of the sizes of the par-

ticles occurs owing to coalescence, being quite typical phenomenon at heat treatment [22].

Fig.6. APM-image in topography mode (a), and three-dimensional image of the surface of heat-treated CdS-PbS film (b).

For an estimation of a roughness of the surface the value of the root-mean-square roughness (R_q) was chosen. It was established, that heat treatment promoted reduction of the roughness value from 81.7 down to 43.0 nm that was almost twice.

It is known, that epitaxial growth of a film is observed only at similarity of a lattice parameters of a substrate material and micro-crystallites deposited on it [23].

At undirected crystallization in case of CdS deposition on glass-ceramic germs start to form on various defects. In order to approximate the character of formation of clusters and aggregates in the film, and also to show the features of their surfaces, the fractal analysis of the surfaces of as-deposited and heat-

treated CdS-PbS films was carried out by processing of APM images with 40×40 microns sizes, with use of Gwyddion software package. It is known, that from positions of fractal-cluster approach to formation of metal sulfide films the important parameter describing the mechanism of growth of a layer at hydrochemical deposition is fractal dimension [24]. The obtained values of fractal dimension for as-deposited and heat-treated films have made accordingly 2.42 and 2.32 that within the framework of Witten-Sander model corresponds mainly to particle-cluster-type aggregation at Brownian motion [25]. The reduction of the given parameter for the heat-treated film was explained by more dense arrangement of particles in aggregates, owing to their integration at heat treatment.

Thus, at hydrochemical deposition the aggregate mechanism of growth consisting in adsorption of relatively large particles by a surface of a growing film was realized [24].

Growth of the film was accompanied by recrystallization as a result of which the most stable orientation of CdS particles formed.

Optical properties of obtained CdS-PbS films of 1 micron thickness were investigated outside of the spectral area of their photoconductivity - in the near and far infrared (IR) areas of a spectrum.

The reflectance spectrums of CdS-PbS films with various ratios of metal sulfides, obtained by incubation of CdS films deposited on glass-ceramic substrates in lead salt solution are shown on fig.7. The spectrum of CdS-PbS film obtained by thermal evaporation in vacuum on mica substrate with subsequent heat treatment on air, and also the reflectance spectrum of substrates are shown for comparison. Reflection from «film+substrate» system was less than from appropriate substrates that, apparently, is connected to absorption of optical radiation in the films. As a rule, the reflection for as-deposited films (1–4, 9) is less, than for the heat-treated (6–8). Especially small reflection was observed at the film obtained by thermal evaporation (10–on the mica). The structure of the spectrum was not examined here in details. Let's note only, that the minimum for a film on mica in the field of 8 microns may be explained by plasma resonance of electrons.

Fig.7. Reflectance spectrums of as-deposited (1–4, 9) and heat-treated (6–8, 10) CdS-PbS films, mica (11), and glass-ceramic (12). The film (10) was obtained by thermal evaporation.

The transmission spectrums of the same films are shown on fig. 8. The feature of the spectrums is low transmission of as-deposited films.

Fig.8. Transmission spectrums of as-deposited (1–4, 9) and heat-treated (6–8, 10) CdS-PbS films, mica (11), and glass-ceramic (12). The film (10) was obtained by thermal evaporation.

Summarizing the results, we can conclude that incubation of chemically deposited CdS films in a lead salt aqueous solution makes it possible to introduce PbS into the thin film, which leads to formation of composites CdS-PbS, including $Pb_xCd_{1-x}S$ substitutional solid solutions. Subsequent thermal treatment of the layers at 423 K increases the lead sulfide content in the solid solutions.

Conclusions:

1. Complex investigation of ionic-exchange process on “CdS film – citrate complex of lead” interphase has been carried out.
2. Modified CdS film has been obtained by incubation in aqueous solution of lead (II) salt. The X-ray analysis of them has shown the presence of $Pb_xCd_{1-x}S$ solid solution in their structure, substitution of cadmium by lead in which increased after heat treatment.
3. The ordering of film’s structures owing to the reduction of micro-deformations at heat treatment has been revealed.
4. The SEM-image analysis of the surfaces of the films has been carried out, the increase of the sizes of micro-particles during thermal processing owing to coalescence, and also the reduction of the roughness of the heat-treated film from 81.7 down to 43.0 nanometers has been revealed.
5. Fractal dimension for as-deposited and heat-treated films which values have made 2.42 and 2.32, accordingly, that for both films according to the Witten-Sander model corresponds to the mechanism of particle-cluster-type formation at Brownian motion has been determined.
6. One of the features of reflectance spectrums of the obtained films was connected to that the film, obtained by hydrochemical deposition on glass-ceramic substrate, differ with a smaller deviation from stoichiometry aside surplus of cadmium in comparison with the film obtained by thermal evaporation on mica. The heat treatment of the last on air did not result in full compensation of cadmium surplus giving the contribution to absorption due to free electrons.

Authors express acknowledgements to M.I. Shishkin and A.A. Skaptsov for the carried out researches of optical properties of semi-conductor films, and also to Professor A.G. Rokach for discussion of the results of this research.

References

- [1] A.G. Rokach, S.V. Stetsyura, A.A. Serdobintsev “Geterofaznye poluprovodniki pod deistviem izlucheniya”. *Izvestiya Saratov. Univ.*, Vol. 5, pp. 92-101, 2005. [In Russian]
- [2] S. Thansavel, S. Ganesan, K. Saravanan “Annealing effect on cadmium in situ doping of chemical bath deposited PbS thin films”. *Thin Solid Films*, Vol. 520, pp. 5206 - 5210, 2012.
- [3] I.V. Malyar, S. V. Stetsyura “The influence of morphology and surface composition on radiation stability of heterogeneous material CdS-PbS”. *Semiconductors*, 45 (7), 916 - 921, 2011.
- [4] G. Mustafa, M.R.I. Chowdhury, D.K. Saha, S. Hussian, O. Islam “Annealing Effects on the Properties of Chemically Deposited CdS thin films at ambient condition”. *Dhaka Univ. J. Sci.*, Vol. 60 (2), pp. 283 - 288, 2012.
- [5] Wug– Dog Park “Structural and optical properties of thermally annealed nanocrystalline CdS Thin Films”. *Journal of the Korean Society*, Vol. 54, No. 5, pp. 1793 - 1797, 2009.
- [6] P.M. Behtke, P.B. Barton “Sub – solidus relation in the system PbS – CdS “. *Amer. Mineralogist*, Vol. 56, pp. 2034 - 2039, 1971.
- [7] P.N. Ivanov, V.F. Markov, L.N. Maskaeva “Role of the Size Effect in Hydrochemical Deposition of PbS–CdS Solid-Solution Films”. *Inorganic materials*, Vol. 41, N 11, pp. 1292 - 1296, 2005.
- [8] Modaffer. A. Mohammed, Ali M. Mousa, J.P. Ponpon “Optical and Optoelectric Properties of PbCdS Ternary Thin Films Deposited by CBD”. *Journal of semiconductor technology and science*, Vol. 9, No. 2, pp. 117 - 123, 2009.
- [9] Z.I. Smirnova, L.N. Maskaeva, V.I. Voronin, V.F. Markov “Synthesis of thin film solid solutions $Pb_{1-x}Sn_xSe$ by means of ion-exchange substitution”. *Butlerov Communications.*, Vol. 21, N 7, pp. 29 - 33, 2010.
- [10] L.N. Maskaeva, E. A. Dubinina, H.N. Mukhamedzyanov, V.F. Markov “Synthesis of $Hg_xPb_{1-x}Se$ solid solutions by ion-exchange substitution”. *Butlerov Communications*, Vol. 27, N 15, pp. 65 - 70, 2011.
- [11] L.N. Maskaeva, V.F. Markov, A.A. Moskalyeva “Making of PbS–Ag₂S thin solid solution films by the method of ion exchange substitution”. *Butlerov Communications* Vol. 26, N 10, pp. 37 - 43, 2011.
- [12] L.N. Maskaeva, Z.I. Smirnova, V.I. Voronin, V.F. Markov “Ion-Exchange Synthesis of Thin Film Substitutional Solid Solutions in the CdS-PbS System” *Fundamental Problems of Modern Materials Science*, Vol. 8, N 3, pp. 55 - 62, 2011 [In Russian].
- [13] G. Hodes “*Chemical Solution Deposition of Semiconductor Films*”. New York: Marcel Dekker, 2002.
- [14] F. Pfisterer “The wet-topotaxial process of junction formation and surface treatments of Cu₂S – CdS thin-film solar cells”. *Thin Solid Films*, Vol. 431 – 432, pp. 470 – 476, 2003.
- [15] M. Sam, M.R. Bayati, M. Mojtahedi, K. Janghorban “Growth of Cu₂S /CdS nano-layered

- photovoltaic junctions for solar cell applications”. *Applied Surface Science*, Vol. 257, pp. 1449 – 1453, 2010.
- [16] M.K. Karanjai, D. Dasgupta “Photoconductive properties of dip-deposited CdS:Cu,Cl thin films sensitized in situ”. *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.*, Vol. 21, pp 1769 – 1772, 1988.
- [17] V.S. Taur, R.A. Joshi, A.V. Ghule, R. Sharma “Effect of annealing on photovoltaic characteristics of nanostructured p-Cu₂S/n-CdS thin film”. *Renewable Energy*, Vol. 38, pp 219-223, 2012.
- [18] M. Ristova, M. Ristov, P. Tosev, M. Mitreski “Silver doping of thin CdS films by an ion exchange process”. *Thin Solid-Films*, Vol. 315, pp. 301-304, 1998.
- [19] Y.Y. Lurie “*Spravochnik po analyticheskoy himii*”. Moscow, Himiya, 1989 [In Russian].
- [20] P. Atkins, J. de Paula “*Atkins’ Physical Chemistry*”. W. H. Freeman and Company, 2006.
- [21] L.M. Kovba “*Rentgenofazoviy analiz*”. Izdat. Mosc. Univ., 1976 [In Russian].
- [22] S. Elmas, S. Ozcan, S. Ozder, V. Bilgin “Influence of annealing temperature on the electrical and optical properties of CdS thin films”. *Acta physica polonica A.*, Vol. 121, No. 1, pp. 56-58, 2012.
- [23] V.V. Treugolov, V.A. Stepanov, G.N. Skoptsova “Issledovanie s pomoshiu atomnosilovoy microscopii poverhnosti tonkih plenok CdS, izgotovlennykh metodom gidrokhimicheskogo osajdeniya”. *Vestnik Ryzanskogo Gos. Univ. imeni S.A.Esenina*, N 35, pp. 153-160, 2012 [In Russian].
- [24] V.F. Markov, L.N. Maskaeva, P.N. Ivanov, “Hydrochemical deposition of films of metal sulfides: modelling and experiment”, Ural Department of the Russian Academy of Science, Ekaterinburg, 2006.
- [25] B.M. Smirnov “*Physica fractalnego clastera*”. Moscow, Nauka, 1991 [In Russian].